

GA No. 953214

H2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2020-twostage
RIA
GRANT AGREEMENT: 953214

Deliverable No. D9.7
Deliverable Title European Citizens Awareness Platform

Document ID D9.7 D 9.7v2.0
Dissemination level Public
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Issue date 02-Dec-22

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Disclaimer and acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under H2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2020-twostage. Grant Agreement 953214 — upPE-T

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The H2020 project has been made possible by a financial contribution by the European Commission under HORIZON 2020.

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Document information

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Document Change Log

Version	Date	Comments
v0.1	26/10/2021	First draft of document
v0.4	28/10/2021	Revised version based on the comments of Fuensanta Monzó Sánchez (CETEC) and Marianna Faraldi (TCA).
v1.0	28/10/2021	First final version, approved by Executive Board, submitted to EC.
v1.1	23/11/2022	Revision based on the 1 st review report.
v1.2	26/11/2022	Internal review by Marianna Faraldi-TCA and Angela Gaitani-MoNS
v2.0	02/12/2022	Second final version, approved by Executive Board, (will be) submitted to EC.

Document Distribution Log

Version	Date	Distributed to
v0.1	26/10/2021	Internal reviewers from up-PET
v0.4	28/10/2021	Coordinator for approval
v1.1	23/11/2022	Internal reviewers from upPE-T
v2.0	02/12/2022	Coordinator for approval

Verification and approval

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Angela Gaitani	02/12/2022
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó	02/12/2022

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2. List of abbreviation

CAP	Communication and awareness plan
ECAP	European citizen awareness platform
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
MOOC	Massive Open Online Courses
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
VR	Virtual Reality

3. Executive summary

The upPET “European citizens awareness platform” is intended as one of the tools implementing the upPE-T citizen awareness strategy and a ‘public forum’ highlighting the upcycling of food and drink plastic packaging.

This deliverable reports on the requirements and high-level framework of the European citizens awareness platform developed in the upPE-T project. The web link where the platform is hosted and its public launch date are mentioned.

4. Introduction

The technical innovations in upPE-T project will have a wider impact by increasing awareness among European citizens of products and materials upcycling and to improve consumers behaviour and attitude towards drink&food packaging recycling and purchasing. The awareness raising is continuously performed in this project supported by the integration of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) disciplines and Responsible Research and Innovation processes (RRI) within overall upPE-T approach.

5. Scope and objective

This Deliverable is an outcome of Task 9.4 which runs until the end of the project. This deliverable focuses on defining the aim, the requirements and the high-level framework of a “European citizens awareness platform” (ECAP).

6. European citizens awareness platform

6.1. What is it and what is the expected function

The upPET “European citizens awareness platform” is intended as a tool implementing the upPE-T citizen awareness strategy and a ‘public forum’ highlighting the upcycling of food and drink plastic packaging.

The platform will be used by the project for:

- Understanding the citizens needs with regards their ability to perceive environmental problems linked to global socio-economics issues.
- Awareness building among the target audience of upPE-T including the European citizens.
- Implementing a continuous, proactive engagement with the European citizens through WP9’s solid communication and awareness strategy that includes the participation of all members of the consortium and Advisory Board, ensuring that relevant information is properly communicated and widely spread among the project’s target audience.

Through the platform, upPE-T partners make an attempt to increase citizens knowledge about environmental threats and challenges, the need of a sustainable economy, and their ability to understand related complex issues as the concept of products and materials upcycling. The goal is to empower the target groups (including citizens) with a tool to increase their ability to understand environmental problems and further increasing their knowledge & awareness regarding materials and products upcycling, and improve

consumer’s attitude and behaviour with respect to purchasing and recycling food & drink packaging.

Key message to spread: Upcycling increases quality and lifetime of materials and products, reduces wastes, creates employment opportunities, and encourages sustainable consumer behaviour. upPE-T project vision is the perfect example for showing the benefits of upcycling, through - for example - the results of the LCA carried out. Moreover, our message will spread the need of packaging recycling and the importance of acquiring packaging from renewable sources to contribute to decarbonise the society.

6.2.Target audience

Although the main target group of the platform is represented by European citizens as a whole, upPE-T puts a specific focus on students and young people, since they represent the main pillars of mid-term and long-term society. Thus, it is essential to provide them the right tools and knowledge to increase their ability to actively participate within global challenges debates. For citizens in general, we will specify tailored messages segregated by the identified target groups and needs, with the aim of increase, in the short term, the knowledge and ability to understand current faced challenges and specifically to understand the key messages we target to spread.

6.3.Requirements of the platform

The overall requirements are categorised into three groups as described in Table 1.

Table 1 – Requirements of the platform

Requirement number	Description
Required functionalities for platform administration	
R1.1	Enable users to access resources from 3 rd party websites (e.g. social media).
R1.2	Access all administrative tools and functionalities from a single interface.
R1.3	Monitor visits and other statistics of the platform (i.e. number of users, time period, etc.). External tool(s) can be used.
R1.4	The following Language packs should be available: English, German, Italian, Spanish, Finnish, Greek, Serbian, Croatian, Turkish. It should be able to input translation to the videos.

R1.5	The possibility to conduct surveys among users in the system. A 3 rd party tool might need to be used and integrated into the platform.
R1.6	Communication through emails should be provided such that users can send questions and opinions.
R1.7	Link to blog posts and other materials outside of the platform should be curated such that European citizens get a wide variety of information through the platform.
Required functionalities for course management	
R2.1	Support for common file formats and the possibility to embed the content of such files, (including: aam, aiff, asf, au, avi, doc, gif, html, htm, jpg, jpeg, jif, mpe, mpg, mpeg, moov, mov, pdf, pps, qt, ra, ram, swa, swf, tiff, txt, wav, wpd, xls, xlsx, docx, ppt, pptx, wma, wmf and wmv), in addition to display and reproduction of the above-mentioned file formats within the platform, subject to the availability of the relevant plug-ins in the installation of the user's browser.
R2.2	If the relevant browser plugin is not installed (or is unavailable), the platform should run an external desktop application to display or play the file.
R2.3	Modern, intuitive and responsive interface.
R2.4	The possibility to create different sections within a course.
R2.5	The possibility to access different content, depending on individual performance and student progress.
R2.6	The possibility to change the course settings and make certain tools and parts of the course content (in)accessible on specific dates and at specific times.
R2.7	The possibility for the admin to archive a portion of the course or the entire course.

R2.8	The possibility of automatic notification to users about new activities, publications, assignments, examinations, tests, or changes in the course.
R2.9	The possibility of self-assessment.
R2.10	The possibility to use different types of questions in tests (including Multiple-choice questions), surveys and polls.
R2.11	Visualisation of the course progress allowing the user to quickly and easily understand where s/he stands in the learning process.
R2.12	The platform must possess a built-in a system for sending and receiving e-mails.
R2.13	The system needs to support the import and export of courses and should support generally accepted Common Learning management system standards: AICC, SCORM ¹ , Experience API, CMI, LTI.
Required functionalities for content management	
R3.1	Landing page about the course, key requirements, time and effort expectations, about the upPE-T project.
R3.2	The possibility to publish publicly available information related to the teacher/professor/project.
R3.3	The possibility to store and manage any type of content from a centralized location where it can be administered, updated and shared.
R3.4	The possibility to keep different versions of the file – the system should be able to automatically save the last version of the document and keep all previous versions. E.g. when content is updated.

¹ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/224085435_Standards_and_specifications_for_e-learning_systems

6.4. Framework of the platform

A high-level framework of the platform is illustrated in Figure 1 showing the operational components.

Figure 1 – Framework and components of the platform.

As seen from the above figure, the requirements have been translated into software components of the platform. All the interfaces for content access, management, and administration are performed over a secure communication channel.

Web analytics of the platform is performed using Google analytics, which monitors all the incoming traffic and provide periodically, reports about the site's performance. Google Search Console has been used to upload the file robots.txt to make easier for Google Robots the indexation.

DIGI is responsible for development, continuous updating, and maintenance of the platform while partners such as IDI and UNC are responsible for providing the contents such as MOOCs. All pages will be optimised for the search engines (SEO) during Year 2 of upPE-T, ensuring that the platform is well positioned in the browsers and search engines.

DIGI will also ensure that the platform is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection including the GDPR.

6.5. Access to the platform

6.5.1 Roles

From a high level usability perspective, there are two roles – user and administrator. For hosting the MOOCs, the user role is further categorised as content creator and learner. Only a single user (identified with the email address contact@digiotouch.com) is given

administrator rights which can moderate the contents posted, deleted contents if they are not following the platform terms and conditions. All others are assigned user role. This follows a standard role based access control (RBAC) policy.

6.5.2 Link for access

The developed platform is publicly linked from <https://uppet.eu/european-citizens-awareness>.

6.5.3 Interactions between user and platform

Users intending to utilise the awareness platform to post a question can add a topic related to the question or search for a previously created topic related to the question.

Users can post a question in the form of a new topic as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Add new topic

All topics are listed in the platform as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Topics listed in the platform

Note that, the user is identified with an email address along with the topic. Therefore, should an user with malintent violate the terms and conditions of the platform, the malcontents can be deleted by the administrator and the email address can be blacklisted.

It is also possible to search a previous topic from a search button as shown in the Figure 3. For example, if the user wants of search for a topic on circular economy, typing 'ci' on the search bar shows a previous topic. If there is no such previous topic, then it shows an empty section.

Figure 3 – Search functionality of the platform

6.6. Timeline for development

The timeline for development is outlined in Table 2.

Table 2 – Timeline for European citizens awareness platform development

Month	Action
M3-M4	Requirements collection for the platform (UNC, IDI, DIGI).
M5-M12	First version of the platform developed and internal testing performed by DIGI.
M14-M17	Second development phase preparing the platform to host, manage, and publish MOOCs.
M24-M48	Launch of the platform for continuous interaction among the citizens, other stakeholders with the platform in line with WP9’s communication and awareness strategies and continuous improvement and maintenance to be performed by DIGI.
M49 onwards	The platform will be merged into DIGI’s Paradise Platform for continuing the public engagement and maintenance of the MOOCs.

6.7. Public launch

The platform has been publicly launched in a webinar organised by the upPE-T partners on 20th October 2022, when the first contents for the platform were developed and available (MOOC and VR app). A recording of the webinar is available at the following link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kLduepLBTHU>.

Since its launch until 22nd November 2022, the monitoring system of the ECAP counts 75 new users with an average engagement time of ~ 8.5 minutes. Such KPIs will be further reported in the upcoming WP9 deliverables.

Figure 1 – Google analytics of the European citizens’ awareness platform.

6.8.Next steps

It is to be noted that T9.4 runs until M48 and, as a result, the platform developed in this task will be continuously improved and maintained throughout the project duration and beyond by DIGI.

During the execution of Task 9.4.1 on awareness roadmap elaboration, it has been decided that the developed platform must also support diffusion of the VR content for the VR mobile app and host, disseminate the MOOCs. Therefore, the developed platform will continue to evolve throughout the duration of the project, maintained by DIGI during and after the project.

6.9.Plan to increase the number of users

A specific plan will be developed at the beginning of year 3, where several actions will be discussed and decided in order to promote the citizens awareness platform and reach the numbers of users established in the project KPIs. Such actions could include:

1. Social media campaign: sharing targeted content on the social media in order to engage and convert people, i.e. publishing the survey with a call to action (CTA), promoting a public event in which they can participate, sharing publication related to the MOOC content in order to convert them into participants.
2. University and schools communication campaign: lessons and meetings with schools and universities students to talk about project-targeted issues, i.e. sharing knowledge, increasing awareness and good practices + examples and activities the can be done directly on the platform (for example: forum discussion - Q&A).
3. Public events: communication and dissemination campaign aimed at engaging people with interactive games to increase their knowledge about certain daily life topics (recycling, waste management etc.) and give them brochures regarding ECAP, so they can easily find more info and in-deep material.

This specific plan will be part of the updated CAP for year 3.

7. Conclusion

In a nutshell, this deliverable reports about the “European citizens awareness platform”, its function, requirements, operational framework, development timeline, and public launch. Users’ initial usage and average time of engagement is also reported. Even if hosted in <https://academy.digiotouch.app>, the platform has been linked to the upPE-T website (<https://uppet.eu/european-citizens-awareness>" <https://uppet.eu/european-citizens-awareness>) to allow a quick and easy access to upPE-T interested parties. It will be updated and maintained by DIGI during and after the project conclusion. In addition, a campaign to advertise the platform and recruit users will start in M24 and continue until the end of the project. Exploitation aspects are under discussion in Task 8.1 activities.